

Experimental evaluation of different heat exchanger typologies for combined thermal-electric refrigeration purposes

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the present work is the experimental characterization of a heat exchanger for application in hybrid sorption-compression cycles for air conditioning and refrigeration purposes. An asymmetric plate heat exchanger was evaluated through a dedicated testing rig under combined evaporator-condenser conditions: the condensation heat released by the compression cycle is then used for evaporation of the refrigerant of the sorption cycle. The effect of operating conditions was evaluated and the experimental results, in terms of achievable heat exchanged and overall heat transfer coefficient are here presented.

Keywords: Refrigeration, low-GWP refrigerant, Evaporators, Hybrid cycles

1. INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest towards the engineering applications of water at low pressures, due to the phase out of several refrigerants after the strict international regulations [1]. Indeed, the application of water as refrigerant has been the focus of intensive research, both for traditional vapour compression and especially in thermally driven systems, such as sorption chillers, heat pumps and storages [2]. In these systems, however, water evaporation occurs at low pressures, i.e. under sub-atmospheric pressures. In these conditions, water is close to its triple point (0.611 kPa, 0.01 °C) and it was experimentally demonstrated that the factors that mostly influence its phase change significantly differ from those observed in water evaporation at higher pressures. Some studies on realistic configurations for evaporators of sorption systems were done in the past years. In [3,4], Giraud et al studied a plate-type configuration for heat exchangers to be used in LiBr/H₂O sorption chillers. Different experiments at various pressures, filling levels and superheating were carried out and correlated to the cooling capacity of the heat exchanger if applied in a sorption chiller. In [5,6], an experimental study on enhanced tubes for application in sorption systems was carried out. The main parameters analysed were filling ratio, superheat, driving forces. The main drawback of such studied is the use of simplified configurations, since a single smooth plate or a single tube are studied as representative pieces of evaporators. However, as already shown in [3], the evaluation of the overall performances of the structure in the real applications of sorption chillers is more challenging. Accordingly, in [7], a lab-scale fin-and-tube aluminium heat exchanger was experimentally tested under pool boiling conditions, but the results indicated that, for the investigated case, the heat transfer was penalised due to the mechanism of evaporation.

In the present paper, the experimental evaluation on a plate-type heat exchanger in lab-scale was carried out under the typical conditions of sorption chiller operation and the heat transfer coefficient and evaporation power for different operating boundaries, in terms of temperatures/pressures are reported.

2. MATERIALS

The tested heat exchanger is a commercial asymmetric plate heat exchanger (HEX) from Alfa Laval company. The results here reported are the preliminary ones from the experimental activity on-going at CNR, and different configurations, in terms of the inclination of the HEX, will be evaluated. The main characteristics of the heat exchanger are reported in [Table 1](#), whereas a picture of the heat exchanger is shown in [Figure 1](#).

Table 1: main features of the heat exchanger tested.

Number of plates / side A	19
Number of plates / side B	20
Volume / side A	2.93 dm ³
Volume / side B	1.88 dm ³
Plate type	dimpled

Material	AISI316
Empty weight	5.57 kg
Overall heat transfer surface	0.78 m ²

Figure 1: the tested heat exchanger.

3. EXPERIMENTAL FACILITIES

The heat exchanger was characterised using a testing stand available at CNR-ITAE, which is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. It works as a condenser operating under the typical conditions of a sorption cycle. It consists of an aluminium flat-tube heat exchanger enclosed in a stainless steel vacuum chamber. The evaporator is connected through a DN50 electrically actuated pneumatic valve for vapour transfer between the evaporator and condenser. At the same time, a pipe for condensate return to the evaporator is used, which is opened at pre-defined time interval through a piloted solenoid valve. The temperature levels for the operation of the condenser and evaporator are supplied by a testing rig, which is described in details in [8]. The heat source for evaporation is an electric heater connected to a 0.5 m³ tank, whereas condensation heat is dumped to a 0.75 m³ storage connected to a water/water chiller. All the circuits are equipped with variable speed pumps and thermally insulated with PU foam. The temperatures in the hydraulic circuits are measured through Pt100 1/10 DIN, whereas the temperature of liquid and vapour in the condenser and evaporator are measured through class A type T thermocouples. Pressure in the components is measured through piezo-capacitive flanged transducers with ± 2 full-scale accuracy. Flow rate in the hydraulic circuits is measured by magnetic mass flow meters with $\pm 2.5\%$ full-scale accuracy.

Figure 2: experimental apparatus used for the characterization of the heat exchanger.

Figure 3: the testing rig at CNR.

3.1. Testing procedure and data reduction

The testing procedure during each test is as follows:

- Pre-conditioning of the condenser and evaporator Heat Transfer Fluid;
- Setting of the desired flow rate and temperature of the HTF;
- Opening of vacuum valves;
- Start of recording;
- After at least 60 minutes of evaporation under stationary conditions (i.e. the fluctuations in the evaporation power are lower than $\pm 20\%$ of the average value, the test is stopped).

The main parameters used to characterize the heat exchanger are the evaporation power and the overall heat transfer coefficient.

The evaporation power was calculated as:

$$\dot{Q}_{evap} = \dot{m} c_p (T_{in} - T_{out}) \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where \dot{m} [kg/s] is the flow rate of the HTF, c_p is its specific heat [kJ/(kgK)] and T_{in} [°C] and T_{out} [°C] are the temperatures of the HTF measured in proximity of the heat exchanger.

The overall heat transfer coefficient was calculated as:

$$U = \frac{\dot{Q}}{S_{tot} \text{LMTD}} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Where S_{tot} is the heat exchange area [m²] and LMTD is the logarithmic temperature difference, defined as:

$$\text{LMTD} = \frac{(T_{in} - T_{out})}{\ln \left(\frac{T_{vap} - T_{in}}{T_{vap} - T_{out}} \right)} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Where T_{vap} [°C] is the temperature of the vapour in the evaporator.

In addition, the overall heat transfer coefficient was separated into its main three components:

- The internal convective heat transfer on the HTF side of the heat exchanger, h_i [W/(m²K)];
- The thermal conduction in the metal of the plate, k_{plate} [W/(mK)];
- The refrigerant side heat transfer, h_{ref} [W/(m²K)].

$$\frac{1}{U} = \frac{1}{h_i} + \frac{l_{fins}}{k_{fins}} + \frac{1}{h_{ext}} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

The internal heat transfer coefficient was calculated as [9]:

$$\frac{1}{h_i} = \frac{D_h}{Nu k_w} \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

Where D_h [m] is the hydraulic diameter, k_w [W/(mK)] is the thermal conductivity of water and Nu is the Nusselt number, which is equal to:

$$Nu_{lam} = 3.6568 \quad (\text{valid for } Re < 2300) \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

$$Nu_{turb} = 0.023 * Re^{\frac{4}{5}} * Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (\text{valid for } Re \geq 10^4) \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

where Re is the Reynolds-number (-) and Pr the Prandtl-number (-) of the HTF.

In the range $2300 < Re < 10^4$ the Nusselt number is calculated according to [9]:

$$Nu_{trans} = (1 - \zeta) Nu_{lam} + \zeta Nu_{turb} \quad \text{Eq. (8)}$$

With:

$$\zeta = \frac{Re - 2300}{10^4 - 2300} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

To correlate the results to the driving forces of the process, some additional parameters were calculated. For instance, the Reynolds number for vapour was calculated as:

$$Re_{vap} = \frac{\rho_{vap} u_{vap} D_h}{\mu} \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

Where ρ_{vap} is the density of the vapour [kg/m³], D_h [m] is the hydraulic diameter, supplied by the producer, μ [Pa s] is the dynamic viscosity and u_{vap} is the velocity of the vapour calculated as:

$$u_{vap} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{evap}}{\Delta H_{evap}} \cdot \frac{1}{S_{port}} \quad \text{Eq. (11)}$$

Where ΔH_{evap} is the enthalpy of evaporation for the refrigerant and S_{port} is the cross-sectional area of the vacuum valve connecting the evaporator and the condenser.

Moreover, Grashof number was calculated as [9]:

$$Gr = \frac{g \beta D_h^3 (T_{HTF} - T_{vap})}{\nu^2} \quad \text{Eq. (12)}$$

Where g is the gravity constant [kg/(m²s)], β [1/K] is the thermal expansion coefficient and ν [m²/s] is the kinematic viscosity.

Grashof and Reynolds numbers can be combined into the Richardson number [9], which gives an idea of the dominating fluid-dynamic phenomenon:

$$Ri = \frac{Gr}{Re^2} \quad \text{Eq. (13)}$$

For $Ri \ll 1$, forced convection is the dominant term, whereas for $Ri > 10$ natural convection is the dominating effect.

Detailed uncertainty of measurements for the sensors used in the testing rig is reported in [7] and is in the range of 8-10% for the tests here presented. Prior to the beginning of the experimental campaign, all thermocouples were calibrated through a dry block calibration system. Moreover, for each condition, at least three tests were done and it was verified that the deviation lies within the uncertainty of measurements.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Typical evolutions

Aim of the tests was the evaluation of the achievable power and heat transfer coefficient under different operating conditions. In particular, all the tests were carried out under vacuum on the vapour side of the heat exchanger, connected to the condenser. Indeed, pressures in the range of 6-9 kPa were measured, corresponding to saturated vapour conditions, typical for the operation of sorption systems [10].

An example of the temperatures measured in the evaporator during a test is given in [Figure 4](#). For the whole test duration, steady-state conditions are achieved and there is not a significant fluctuation of the temperatures of the HTF and the vapour. The temperature of the vapour in the condenser is almost equal to the vapour temperature in the evaporator, i.e. only 1.5-2.0 K lower whereas the temperature of the liquid in the component is set to a much lower value.

Figure 4: temperature evolutions for a typical test.

All the contributions to the overall heat transfer coefficient calculated according to what reported in section 3.1 are shown in Figure 5 (up). As expected, the dominating contribution is the heat transfer coefficient on the refrigerant (vapour) side of the HEX, which is further shown in Figure 5 (down). The coefficient on the HTF side is around $35000 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ ($Re \approx 57000$), indicating that turbulent conditions are achieved, which are essential for a good heat transfer in these systems. Instead, it is possible to notice that the heat transfer coefficient on the refrigerant side keeps almost constant for the whole test duration and around $600 \text{ W/(m}^2\text{K)}$. The reasons for the fluctuations of the heat transfer coefficient are probably due to the specific testing procedure used for keeping the amount of liquid in the evaporator constant: the solenoid valve installed on the condensate pipe is open for 3 seconds and subsequently closed for 3 seconds. A dedicated set of tests was preliminarily carried out to make sure this was the optimal time for guaranteeing steady-state operation of the evaporator without any dry out or flooding effects. However, this means that there is a liquid transfer for some seconds that has an influence on the pressure and temperatures measured and, ultimately, prevents from a completely flat and steady behaviour. Nonetheless, since the final evaluation of each test is done on the average parameters, the influence of such a peculiar behaviour is negligible.

Figure 5: heat transfer coefficient evolution for a reference test. Up: all contributions and overall heat transfer coefficient; Down: heat transfer coefficient of refrigerant.

Finally, the temporal evolution of evaporation power is shown in Figure 6: even though a constant overall value of about 1.2 kW is kept, the same fluctuations observed in the heat transfer coefficient occur also for this parameter.

Figure 6: evaporation power for a reference test.

4.2. Effect of operating conditions

The effect of operating conditions is evaluated by varying the driving force available for the process, which is essentially the pressure difference between evaporator and condenser [7]. Accordingly, a set of tests was carried out with constant HTF inlet to the evaporator (set to 45°C) and variable HTF inlet to the condenser. The results are reported in Figure 7. It is possible to notice that, passing from 7°C to 22°C of inlet temperature, the effect on the heat transfer coefficient for the evaporator is not particularly marked, with values are in the range of 580-650 W/(m²K). Nonetheless, the effect of changing the operating pressure is partially visible for very low inlet temperatures (i.e. the case of 7°C), where a higher heat transfer coefficient was measured (about 700 W/(m²K)) due to the higher pressure difference. A reduction is instead visible for higher temperatures, corresponding to the lower pressure difference between condenser and evaporator.

Figure 8 shows the evaporation power calculated as a function of LMTD, calculated according to Eq. 3. A linear trend is observed, which gives an indication on the possible characteristic correlation for the sizing of the heat exchanger according to temperature conditions.

Figure 7: effect of driving force on heat transfer coefficient for the evaporator.

Figure 8: evaporation power as a function of Reynolds number for vapour.

4.3. Discussion

Results of tests were further analysed according to the Richardson number defined above in Eq. 13. As shown in Figure 9, Ri is always much lower than 0.1 on the refrigerant side, thus indicating that turbulent convection is the dominating mechanism inside the heat exchanger, thus guaranteeing that good heat transfer is achieved for all the examined conditions.

Figure 9: evaporation power as a function of Ri .

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the results on the experimental characterization of an asymmetric plate heat exchanger as an evaporator for sorption systems are presented. The peculiarity of the investigation is the use of the heat exchanger as an evaporator for water at sub-atmospheric pressures. The effect of pressure difference between the condenser and the evaporator was evaluated. Results indicated that the overall heat transfer coefficient is in the range of 550-650 W/(m²K) and an evaporation power of 900 to 1200 W was measured. The dominating convection regime is turbulent both on HTF and water vapour side, as indicated by a Richardson number-based estimation.

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NOMENCLATURE

c_p	Specific heat, kJ/(kg K)	Greek letters	
D_h	Hydraulic diameter, m	ρ	Density, kg/m ³
Gr	Grashof number	μ	Dynamic viscosity, Pa s
h	Heat transfer coefficient, W/(m ² K)	ν	Kinematic viscosity, m ² /s
H	Enthalpy, kJ	Subscripts	

k	Thermal conductivity, W/(mK)		
$LMTD$	Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference, K	in	inlet
m	Mass, kg	lam	laminar
\dot{m}	Mass flow, kg/s	out	outlet
Nu	Nusselt number	turb	turbulent
p	Pressure, Pa	vap	vapour
\dot{Q}	Thermal Power, kW	Abbreviations	
Re	Reynolds Number	HEX	Heat Exchanger
Ri	Richardson number	HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
S	Surface, m ²		
t	Time, s		
T	Temperature, °C		
U	Overall heat transfer coefficient, W/(m ² K)		

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ANSWERS TO REVIEWERS

Reviewer 2:

The manuscript presents some experimental tests on an asymmetric plate heat exchanger under different operating conditions. The work is very interesting, although I suggest that the authors make some changes. The title talks about "different heat exchanger typologies", but in the paper I find only one heat exchanger. I think this point needs to be explained better.

The following explanation was added: "The results here reported are the preliminary ones from the experimental activity on-going at CNR, and different configurations, in terms of the inclination of the HEX, will be evaluated."

I suggest the Authors to add an uncertainty calculation, for instance on thermocouples, thermal-resistances, heat transfer coefficient, etc. Since the internal heat transfer coefficient was obtained through a correlation and not through a direct measurement, I think it is appropriate to calibrate the system before providing the results, for example through a first principle heat transfer balance. I also suggest the Authors to publish some repeatability tests.

The following explanation was added: "Detailed uncertainty of measurements for the sensors used in the testing rig is reported in [7] and is in the range of 8-10% for the tests here presented. Prior to the beginning of the experimental campaign, all thermocouples were calibrated through a dry block calibration system. Moreover, for each condition, at least three tests were done and it was verified that the deviation lies within the uncertainty of measurements."

Finally, I ask the Authors to format the manuscript according to the conference rules.

The manuscript was updated accordingly.